

**PRODUCTION OF ALTERNATIVE DEADLINES FOR PLANTING
RICE IN THE PLANT METHOD AS THE MAIN CROP**

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Annotation: The article information about the cultivation technology, demand for moisture, heat and alternative planting dates of the rice plant grown in the conditions of the Surhkondaryo region.

Key words: Application of microelements, dry mass, selectivity and genetics, Vegetative and generative period.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the emphasis on agricultural development on the Earth is increasing from year to year. In particular, in 2017-2021, agricultural gross output increased by 6.8 percent. The average annual growth rate of production during this period was about 1.7 percent. In 2017-2021, agriculture's per-occupant added value increased by 7.0 percent, up 60 percent from the 2019 average World rate. Uzbekistan ranks first among Central Asian countries in terms of population density-1 kv.km.ha there were 51.4 people. There are 8 inhabitants of the Republic per hectare of irrigated land. The population growth rate is much higher than the growth rate of the irrigated land area. Therefore, the area of irrigated land per capita in the last 30 years, from 0.23 hectares to 0.16 hectares due to population growth, has decreased by almost 25 percent. Together with the development of a number of crops in Uzbekistan, measures were organized aimed at developing the rice plant and creating new varieties. In particular, the draft resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on additional measures for the

Sustainable Development of rice farming «was published for discussion. This means that we need to work more tirelessly on agricultural workers. The processes of growth and development are considered of great importance in the planting of a rice plant, in which the basis of grain formation is laid. Knowing how to go through the stages of development in the of a rice plant is considered extremely important. The concrete agro technical measures adapted to obtain a high yield from rice are counted in a timely manner.(Application of microelements, fungicides and growth adjusters, application of nitrogen fertilizers, and act) on the rice, it is necessary to clearly pass all agro technical activities according to the stages of the development of the plant, paying attention to the place of the stages in the formation of the characteristic, and the conditions required to pass it must be noted, paying attention to the place of the alexia stages in the formation of the, it is necessary that the conditions required for its passage be noted, otherwise, if these conditions are broken, a decrease in specificity will be observed. The pre-spring (stem growth) period of rice development is in vegetative development, is in generative development until the end of budding and flowering, and is in reproductive development at the beginning of ripening and when fully ripe. During the Vegetative period, the root, stem and leaf grow, during the generative period, the grain absorbs water.

MAIN BODY

Through the seed shell, water passes into the murky. When a rice seedling is moved to another place, of course, the tip of the head vein is severed, and this is a kind of jarring state of anthropogenic influence shown by a young person, changing the subsequent growth, development and other physiological processes of the plant, spoiling, looking at the point of rain selection and genetic defect, the plant is modeficized, moving to a different state, When the inner part of the Rice head Root is absorbed, the side roots grow rapidly, new ones begin to appear darkly, and the same opportunities for the side stems come to the face. It is known that the side roots are located on the upper, surface part of the soil, do not tend to grow and penetrate towards the deep layer, and spread along the facial layer, and from dormant calm shoots,

additional side roots and side stems begin to appear in large numbers. The rice root penetrates to a depth of up to 1 m if the tip is not interrupted. In rice cultivation, to study the effect of planting periods on the growth and development of rice tops and subsoil sections, increasing the dry mass, during the water period, five pieces of rice seedlings from each option are taken with the root and the height and the increase in dry vase are observed. N.N. Silanteva believes (1991) that the height of the plant is almost the same, regardless of the amount of past crop or menial fertilizers during the germination period, and the main reason for this is due to the fact that the nutrient elements that are needed in the growth processes of the germination period are obtained mainly from the endosperm.

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